

Vertical distribution and habitat use in arboreal scorpions from a tropical rainforest in Costa Rica

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Online supplemental material

Supplementary tables:

Supplementary Table 1: Abbreviations and explanations of the measured variables.

Abbr.	Meaning
HS	Absolute height of a scorpion above ground
rHS	Relative height of a scorpion, $rHS = HS/HT$
Inst	Instar classes: subadult/adult, large juvenile, small juvenile
D	Scorpion density on tree, $D = \text{Scorpion abundance}/HT$; per tree and survey run
HT	Total height of a surveyed tree
H _{Anchor}	Height of the anchor crotch for the climbing rope
HLB	Height of the lowest branch
rHLB	Relative height of the lowest branch, $rHLB = HLB/HT$
DBH	Trunk diameter in breast height (1.5 m) or if large buttress roots then just above them
EpTr	Number of epiphytes on the trunk below the lowest branch
EpCr	Number of epiphytes on the trunk and branches \geq height of the lowest branch Classes: 0 = none, 1 = few ($\leq 20\%$), 2 = many (ca 20 – 50%), 3 = almost full ($\geq 50\%$)
Ep	Total number of epiphytes per tree, mean of EpTr and EpCr
HoTr	Number of holes in the trunk below the lowest branch, usually below the first 3m
HoCr	Number of holes in the trunk and branches \geq height of the lowest branch Classes: 0 = none, 1 = some, 2 = few, 3 = many
Ho	Total number of holes per tree, mean of HoTr and HoCr
T, RH	Temperature (T) and relative air humidity (RH) at 28 m above ground during the time of surveying a tree for scorpions, averaged over three trees
VPD	Vapor pressure deficit calculated from T-RH-pairs
Prec	Monthly total precipitation

Supplementary Table 2: Characteristics of the trees surveyed. ^L= trees with data loggers at 1 and 28 m height, * = excluded tree, see texts. For abbreviations of the variables see SupplementaryTable 1.

Tree species	Abbr.	DBH [cm]	HT [m]	H _{Anchor} [m]	HLB [m]	rHLB	EpTr	EpCr	HoTr	HoCr
<i>Alchorneopsis floribunda</i> , Euphorbiaceae	Af	45	29	24.5	15.3	0.5	1	2	2	0
<i>Ceiba pentandra</i> , Malvaceae	Cp2	130	45	38.8	31.2	0.7	3	3	1	0
<i>Ceiba pentandra</i> , Malvaceae	Cp3	120	47	40.1	32.2	0.7	3	3	1	0
<i>Ceiba pentandra</i> , Malvaceae	Cp1	140	45	38.2	32	0.7	3	3	1	0
<i>Humiriastrum diguense</i> , Humiriaceae	Hd1	70	27	21.6	14	0.5	3	3	2	0
<i>Humiriastrum diguense</i> , Humiriaceae	Hd2	75	32	25.1	15.4	0.5	2	2	1	0
<i>Luehea seemannii</i> , Malvaceae	Ls1	200	26	18.5	5.3	0.2	3	3	3	0
<i>Luehea seemannii</i> , Malvaceae	Ls2 ^L	120	39	34.2	14.9	0.4	3	3	3	1
<i>Pentaclethra macroloba</i> , Fabaceae	Pm1	100	31	25.3	16.6	0.5	2	2	3	1
<i>Pentaclethra macroloba</i> , Fabaceae	Pm2	80	31	26.8	12.3	0.4	2	3	2	0
<i>Pentaclethra macroloba</i> , Fabaceae	Pm5*	60	30	25.9	12	0.4	3	2	2	0
<i>Pentaclethra macroloba</i> , Fabaceae	Pm3	60	27	21.6	11	0.4	3	2	2	0
<i>Pentaclethra macroloba</i> , Fabaceae	Pm4*	80	33	27.8	12.3	0.4	2	1	1	0
sp1	spI	40	32	27.5	23.3	0.7	2	3	1	0
sp2	spII	50	36	30.3	22.6	0.6	1	0	2	0
<i>Tapirira guianensis</i> , Anacardiaceae	Tg	60	29	24.6	13.2	0.5	1	0	1	0
<i>Terminalia oblonga</i> , Combretaceae	Tob	95	38	31.9	20.4	0.5	0	1	2	1
<i>Virola koschnyi</i> , Myristicaceae	Vk	65	35	31.2	21.7	0.6	2	2	0	0
<i>Vitex cooperi</i> , Lamiaceae	Vc ^L	130	39	31	18	0.5	2	3	3	3
<i>Vochysia guatemalensis</i> , Vochysiaceae	Vg1 ^L	90	37	31.4	17.2	0.5	1	1	0	0
<i>Vochysia guatemalensis</i> , Vochysiaceae	Vg2	80	36	31	17.8	0.5	1	2	0	0
<i>Vochysia guatemalensis</i> , Vochysiaceae	Vg3	50	31	26.2	21.9	0.7	1	1	0	0

Supplementary Table 3: Summary of the stepwise forward regressions with relative height of the scorpions as dependent and structural variables of the host trees and vapour pressure deficit in 28 m as independent variables. * variable removed in the process.

C. limbatus

$F_{\text{enter}} = 4.00$ $P = 0.048$ $F_{\text{remove}} = 3.90$ $P = 0.051$

Step #	Vars. entered	R	R ²	Delta R ²	P
1	Epiphytes in crown	0.22	0.049	0.049	0.013

T. pachyurus

$F_{\text{enter}} = 4.00$ $P = 0.069$ $F_{\text{remove}} = 3.90$ $P = 0.072$

Step #	Vars. entered	R	R ²	Delta R ²	P
1	Holes in trunk	0.68	0.47	0.47	0.01

T. ocelote

$F_{\text{enter}} = 4.00$ $P = 0.046$ $F_{\text{remove}} = 3.90$ $P = 0.049$

Step #	Vars. entered	R	R ²	Delta R ²	P
1	Epiphytes trunk	0.24	0.056	0.056	0.028
2	Holes trunk	0.31	0.093	0.037	<0.001
3	Holes crown*	0.36	0.13	0.036	0.085
4	VPD 28m	0.39	0.15	0.021	<0.001
5	Epiphytes crown	0.4	0.16	0.013	<0.001
6	DBH	0.42	0.18	0.016	<0.001
7	Holes crown*	0.42	0.17	-0.0048	

Supplementary figures:

Supplementary Fig. 1: Map of Reserva Biológica Tirimbina showing the locations of the surveyed trees. Abbreviations of tree species are given in Supplementary Table 2.

